

The Matter of the Soul | Symphony Performance
Performance length: 1 hour

#opensource #creativecommons #artscience #music #installation #arctic #empathy #melting
#migration #cassettes

The Matter of the Soul | Symphony is a performance work by Kat Austen that engenders empathy with a consequence of climate change: the process of dispersal and transformation in the Arctic region. The work draws together stories of ecological and cultural change through human migration and melting ice in the Arctic, with changing identity on and offline. During the performance, Austen plays music using samples of water collected in the Arctic during a field trip around Baffin Island in Canada alongside local water samples.

The Matter of the Soul | Symphony explores the impact of human movement on the region's culture and individuals' identities, and reflects on the environmental changes interwoven with this process¹. The raw material and compositions from the project are released online under CC-BY-SA 4.0, with a call for others to remix the work's identity as it travels the internet.

The musical compositions for *The Matter of the Soul* are based around audio field recordings of Arctic waters made using scientific equipment, pH and conductivity meters, that have been hacked to produce sound. The acidity and salinity of Arctic waters vary depending on the melting of ice that increases the amount of fresh liquid water in the Arctic. By taking sounds from these measurements, captures the way that climate change is affecting this fragile region. Austen weaves the story of the ice with human stories related to climate and cultural change in this region using samples from interviews with visitors to and inhabitants of Baffin Island and Resolute.

[Listen on Bandcamp](#)

[The Matter of the Soul performance reel on Vimeo](#)

¹ Austen, K., "Sounding Dispersal as a Route to Empathy with the Changing Arctic", *Leonardo Music Journal* (2019), 29 pp 3-7 https://doi.org/10.1162/lmj_a_01054

Performing at Climate Hub, Klub Królestwo, COP24, Katowice, Poland

At Climate Hub, Klub Królestwo, COP24, Katowice, Poland with Kasia Witek and dancers

Performance Types

1. Solo performance Kat Austen accompanied by video and/or Lightbox installation
Either the entire Symphony performance or just 1-2 movements,

2. Performance with choreography Kat Austen with Kasia Witek and dancers, accompanied by video and/or Lightbox installation
Full Symphony performance with choreography by Kasia Witek and dancers.

3. Performance with collaborating musicians - Kat Austen with pianist and cornet / trumpet, accompanied by video and/or Lightbox installation
Full Symphony performance with an improv pianist and cornet player. Last performed with Matthew Bourne and Alex Bonney.

4. Performance with guest VJ - Kat Austen plus guest VJ
Either the entire performance or 1-2 movements with a VJ remixing the video

Selected performances of *The Matter of the Soul*

- *dissipation and multifurcation* performance, Berliner Gazette's 20th Anniversary Gala, **Zk/U Berlin**, Germany, 12th October 2019
- *concentration* performance, **Deep Sea – Empathie**, Kosmetiksalon Babette, Kindl Brauerei, Berlin, 9th May 2019
- *dissipation and multifurcation* | *The Matter of the Soul*, Hydro_Performance Night at Art Laboratory Berlin at the closing of **Watery Ecologies** exhibition, 16th March 2019
- *Symphony* at the opening of Climate Hub by Greenpeace for **COP24**, Klub Królestwo, Katowice, Poland, 1st December 2018 with Kasia Witek and dancers
- *Symphony* at Howard Assembly Rooms, **Opera North, Leeds**, UK 23rd October 2018 with Matthew Bourne on piano and Alex Bonney on cornet
- *biphasic* | *The Matter of the Soul* at **Headlands Center for the Arts**, San Francisco, 8th September 2018
- *biphasic and concentration* | *The Matter of the Soul* at **Music Tech Fest**, Reactor Hall 1, Stockholm, Sweden, 3rd September 2018 with Servando Barreiro on video
- *concentration* | *The Matter of the Soul* performance 28th June 2018, at **Fusion Festival**
- *concentration* | *The Matter of the Soul* performance 3rd March 2018, as part of **Alien Organs: Sonic Vibrations** at Spektrum, Berlin 2-4 April with Hiroshi Matoba on video

Acknowledgements:

The Matter of the Soul was begun during Austen's [Artist in the Arctic residency with Friends of Scott Polar Research Institute](#) in 2017. She continued its development as [Cultural Fellow in Art and Science](#) at the University of Leeds' Cultural Institute. Made with support from the Polar Museum, Ice Alive, One Ocean Expeditions, Opera North and Bonhams.

About Kat Austen:

Austen is a Berlin-based performance and installation artist. She is a trained pianist and singer and has performed musically over a period of 20 years. Kat Austen's work focusses on interrogating the boundary between what we think of as the self and other(s). Her work relates to redefining and enriching our relationship to the environment, with a particular focus on climate change. She has explored our relationship to the environment through both performance and sculptural mixed and multi-media installations.

Austen was Cultural Fellow in Art and Science at the University of Leeds, 2018 and 2017-18 Artist in the Arctic for Friends of SPRI / Scott Polar Research Institute, sponsored by Bonhams and

Kat Austen | iam@katausten.com

The Matter of the Soul

OneOcean. She lectures on art and citizen science at University College London's Art and Science BAsc, and Engineering Thinking at UCL. Kat holds a Ph.D. in Chemistry from University College London and the Royal Institution of Great Britain.